

CORDIS Results Pack on innovative bioeconomy solutions

Strengthening the EU's prosperity through sustainable and circular bioeconomy innovations

A thematic collection of innovative EU-funded research results

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Editorial

Sustainable and circular bioeconomy innovations can help safeguard our quality of life and deliver benefits for people, planet and prosperity. Bioeconomy innovations will reduce Europe's dependency on non-renewable resources and imports, and reinforce the connection between the economy, society and the environment. They contribute to climate change mitigation and adaptation, while enhancing sustainable competitiveness of European industries and businesses. This CORDIS Results Pack features 15 EU-funded research and innovation projects in the field of bioeconomy, showcasing a wide range of benefits, from reducing environmental impacts to generating jobs.

Bioeconomy solutions work with renewable biological resources to conserve, restore, produce or consume food, materials, products or energy, including through cutting-edge technologies. They contribute to increased circularity, minimising waste and pollution, and maximising the use of materials and side streams, increasing the lifespan of products for as long as possible.

By combining these two approaches, the sustainable and circular bioeconomy supports the EU in achieving its climate and renewable energy goals by 2030, and climate neutrality (net-zero greenhouse gas emissions) by 2050. Fossil dependency and pollution are reduced by substituting fossil-based materials and fuels with bio-based alternatives, while the vitality of rural areas is increased, and biodiversity loss combatted. Europe's farmers, forest owners and actors in the blue bioeconomy have invested significantly into bioeconomy solutions and are committed to scale them up in the future. Europe's innovators have developed technologies and products that are independent from fossil resources, save biomass, energy or water, thereby helping to clean the environment and protect ecosystems.

These bioeconomy innovations will transform the way Europe uses and values biological resources, and promote a more sustainable, resilient and competitive economy.

Leveraging Europe's biological resources

This overview of projects focuses on results that contribute to Europe's position as the continent leading on bioeconomy solutions. These include making the most of biological materials, fostering the strategic management of biomass within ecological boundaries while driving the green transition.

Bioeconomy solutions are deeply rooted in research and innovation and include biotechnologies that contribute to Europe's competitiveness while not posing risks to consumers or the environment. This overview highlights the circularity potential of the bioeconomy by demonstrating the efficient use of biomass side streams and waste, bringing innovations out of the laboratory into the marketplace, and promoting the importance of bioeconomy governance and education.

The Pack highlights 15 projects funded under the EU's Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe research programmes that are making an important contribution to bioeconomy. These initiatives demonstrate how innovations are successfully brought from 'lab to fab' and then to market, stressing the importance of bio-based materials, biotech, bioeconomy governance and education in achieving sustainable prosperity.

Certifiably more sustainable and circular industrial bio-based systems

The innovative BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool (BMT) assesses the effectiveness, robustness and comprehensiveness of sustainability certification schemes and labels for industrial bio-based systems.

Industrial bio-based systems use renewable biological resources to produce bio-based products and materials. A plethora of sustainability certification schemes and labels (CSLs) exist to allow traceability and transparency of sustainability impacts along value chains and trading, within the EU and globally.

Given the rapid proliferation of these schemes, methods to evaluate their performance is crucial. The EU-funded SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project developed a methodology to assess the effectiveness, robustness and comprehensiveness of existing sustainability CSLs for industrial bio-based systems. It is part of the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool (BMT)

being jointly developed by three Horizon Europe projects: SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, STAR4BBS and HARMONITOR.

Meeting sustainability and circularity requirements

The BMT evaluates requirements on three levels: system (governance, transparency and operational robustness), content (sustainability and circularity) and outcome (implementation impacts). SUSTCERT4BIOBASED led the BMT content level development.

"SUSTCERT4BIOBASED focused equally on the three pillars of sustainability – environmental, social and economic – and included circularity aspects such as resource efficiency and recyclability as a fourth category. The BMT content level provides assessment of each CSL based on the fraction of applicable requirements (dependent on the CSL's scope) covered in these four categories," explains project coordinator Iris Vural Gursel of Wageningen Research.

The BMT was tested on nine selected international and EU schemes and labels. Rather than comparing the CSLs, the project assessed them individually to identify opportunities for each CSL owner to enhance their schemes' performance, encouraging them to do so.

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED used 'true cost accounting' to incorporate externalities as well – environmental and social costs and benefits which are not reflected in transaction prices and generally not included in cost-benefit analyses.

training and audit fees, while internal benefits include price premiums and an improved market position. "SUSTCERT4BIOBASED used 'true cost accounting' to incorporate externalities as well – environmental and social costs and benefits which are not reflected in transaction prices and generally not included in cost-benefit analyses," explains Vural Gursel.

A cost-benefit analysis of adopting CSLs in sugar cane, cotton and wood bio-based value chains showed that internal benefits generally outweighed internal costs. Analyses of externalities were impeded by a lack of data, both due to organisations' reluctance to share it and lack of voluntary measurements.

"Further research is needed, which will require standardised reporting requirements on key environmental and social externalities across certification schemes for bio-based value chains," underscores Vural Gursel.

Insights and recommendations based on assessment results

The assessments showed that the CSLs generally addressed the requirements in social and environmental categories, with economic and circularity categories receiving less emphasis. Suggested improvements to the social category include explicit requirements on fair contract practices, social security benefits and maternity leave. Inclusion of more explicit requirements on greenhouse gas emission reporting, air quality monitoring, energy use efficiency and renewable energy use would be positive additions to the environmental category.

More specific requirements on business plans, record keeping of fraudulent practices and economic risk management could improve the CSLs' coverage in the economic category. Circularity requirements beyond waste management, such as the reuse or recycling of residual flows and resource efficiency, are recommended. Furthermore, CSLs for bio-based products could include requirements on design for recyclability and strategies for product-life extension.

Cost-benefit analysis leveraging 'true cost accounting'

Adopting CSLs is voluntary so cost-benefit analyses are key. Internal costs of certification include costs for compliance, such as

Uniting efforts on CSLs

The outcomes were used to provide recommendations to the four key target groups: policy makers, CSL owners, industrial actors and regional bioeconomy actors. With everyone on the same page about the current state and future direction of certification schemes, Europe's path to a green transition to a circular and sustainable bioeconomy just got shorter.

PROJECT
SUSTCERT4BIOBASED – Sustainability Certification for Biobased Systems

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RESULTS PACK ON MICROBIAL BLUEPRINTS FOR BIOECONOMY

Europe is building its bioeconomy using renewable biological resources, such as microorganisms, crops and forests, to produce food supplies, industrial materials and energy resources. The resulting new green value chains and cost-effective industrial processes will help boost the wider economy while protecting biodiversity and the environment. This CORDIS Results Pack showcases the application of 12 EU-funded projects in this field, with benefits ranging from improved soil and ecosystem health to new high-value bio-based products.

Check out the Pack here:
cordis.europa.eu/article/id/459614